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The self-consistent field (SCF) energies, zero-point energies (ZPE), and expectation values of S^2 operator of the final structures optimized at DFT/TPSSh-D3/TZVP level

	SCF energy	ZPE	$\langle S^2 \rangle$
OH	-75.763236	0.0083338	0.752
H₂O	-76.453624	0.0211043	0.000
S1	-539.75986	0.1922026	0.000
S2	-615.56505	0.2062152	0.784
S3	-615.51897	0.2051902	0.786
S4	-614.99264	0.1956476	0.000
S5	-615.57345	0.2058609	0.779
S6	-615.00716	0.1969244	0.000
S7	-690.80821	0.2104514	0.790
S8'	-690.74061	0.2067023	0.784
S8''	-690.74741	0.2074422	0.786
S8	-690.74542	0.2072073	0.785
S9	-690.81581	0.2084304	0.784
S10	-615.56283	0.2058867	0.791
S11	-614.89132	0.1919146	2.048
S12 (triplet)	-614.87584	0.1924402	2.028
S12 (singlet)	-614.95347	0.1967288	0.000
S13	-614.92832	0.1951257	0.000
S14'	-690.12369	0.1976486	2.026
S14 (triplet)	-690.14859	0.1950481	2.023
S14 (singlet)	-690.20964	0.1972337	0.000
S15	-614.92977	0.1956836	0.000
S16 (singlet)	-614.95093	0.1955385	0.000
S16 (triplet)	-614.90372	0.1935149	2.019
S17	-614.84125	0.1915141	2.047
TS 2→3	-615.51199	0.2044376	0.781
TS 2→5	-615.49941	0.2009406	0.767
TS 7→8'	-690.73394	0.2069352	0.772

TS 8''→8	-690.73310	0.2073675	0.803
TS 8→9	-690.70961	0.2057281	0.786
TS 10→11	-691.33197	0.2112695	2.049
TS 11→12	-614.86956	0.1915705	2.035
TS 12→13	-614.92831	0.1947305	0.000
TS 12→15	-614.89166	0.1938621	0.000
TS 15→16	-614.92859	0.1942565	0.000

The xyz format coordinates of the structures calculated at DFT/TPSSh-D3/TZVP level

OH

2

Energy = -75.7632357

H	0.0000000	0.0000000	-0.4897783
O	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.4897783

H₂O

3

Energy = -76.4536239

H	0.7629985	0.0000000	0.1969367
O	0.0000000	0.0000000	-0.3938734
H	-0.7629985	0.0000000	0.1969367

Structure 1

24

Energy = -539.759861

C	-0.0427645	0.0008877	0.0476257
C	0.0374206	0.0002074	1.4563630
C	1.2538158	-0.0007005	2.1078023
C	2.4519664	-0.0009370	1.3754620
C	2.4071737	-0.0000672	-0.0013645
C	1.1750217	0.0008320	-0.6901602
H	-0.8693707	0.0001621	2.0477484
H	1.2831384	-0.0013111	3.1917057
H	3.4050258	-0.0018920	1.8924719
H	3.3257072	-0.0002381	-0.5797368
C	1.1383664	0.0010944	-2.1210965
C	-0.0406556	0.0005842	-2.7931944
C	-1.2905807	0.0002617	-2.0957776
H	2.0802829	0.0014156	-2.6600351
H	-0.0568123	0.0004274	-3.8782979
C	-2.5109773	-0.0010069	-2.8051620
C	-3.7186334	-0.0010933	-2.1424723
C	-3.7383981	0.0002554	-0.7383534
C	-2.5580430	0.0013788	-0.0236757
C	-1.3049022	0.0010994	-0.6723007
H	-2.4810198	-0.0019406	-3.8900981
H	-4.6488472	-0.0021943	-2.6994307

H	-4.6859957	0.0003587	-0.2111177
H	-2.6053705	0.0024163	1.0580947

Structure 2

26

Energy = -615.56505

C	-1.9382207	-3.1731408	-0.1923491
C	-1.8925637	-2.7113874	1.1310414
C	-1.1958527	-1.5478154	1.4420139
C	-0.5213318	-0.8101347	0.4664927
C	-0.5405386	-1.2947317	-0.8847537
C	-1.2767899	-2.4771819	-1.1797600
C	0.1590950	-0.6267151	-1.8947424
C	1.0110535	0.5666070	-1.6575631
C	0.9008179	1.1169181	-0.2500346
C	1.5499621	2.3211540	0.0298071
C	1.4988118	2.8858392	1.2957672
C	0.7855561	2.2362558	2.3037058
C	0.1365026	1.0424579	2.0359908
C	0.1814248	0.4484766	0.7604646
H	-2.4858329	-4.0769500	-0.4347480
H	-2.4013844	-3.2583694	1.9163815
H	-1.1828481	-1.2181942	2.4733909
H	-1.2945284	-2.8293009	-2.2060039
H	0.1267590	-1.0017798	-2.9126468
H	2.0612060	0.3095473	-1.8536389
H	2.0823583	2.8183389	-0.7733713
H	2.0068733	3.8219822	1.4979756
H	0.7298899	2.6663620	3.2976360
H	-0.4227563	0.5683163	2.8326948
H	-0.1640899	1.8656742	-2.5417783
O	0.7580395	1.5906970	-2.6529932

Structure 3

26

Energy = -615.5189739

C	-0.9229496	2.4304520	-2.5318711
C	-1.2513910	3.0344716	-1.3135910
C	-0.9960053	2.3924788	-0.1077531
C	-0.4032141	1.1238373	-0.1223458
C	-0.0904145	0.5110386	-1.3608046
C	-0.3450623	1.1597627	-2.5601496
C	0.4535066	-0.8557215	-1.1341132
C	-0.5260244	-1.7833654	-0.4914310
C	0.5237221	-0.9992722	0.4028619
C	1.4416996	-1.7764051	1.2236827
C	1.5903990	-1.4491000	2.5424795
C	0.9287910	-0.3297072	3.1154442
C	0.1872202	0.5429454	2.3128867
C	0.0343675	0.2761008	0.9644897
H	-1.1234752	2.9511676	-3.4613675

H	-1.7060880	4.0189223	-1.3112864
H	-1.2454243	2.8726295	0.8320473
H	-0.1005533	0.6895177	-3.5066408
H	1.2188034	-1.2742739	-1.7822605
H	-1.5596427	-1.4732311	-0.3980047
H	1.9466740	-2.6427420	0.8108713
H	2.2380832	-2.0519819	3.1700551
H	1.0611803	-0.1150100	4.1690561
H	-0.2084868	1.4607980	2.7355361
H	0.4545748	-3.4066290	-0.9022293
O	-0.4377181	-3.1634319	-0.6233840

Structure 4

25

Energy = -614.9926433

C	-1.1840372	2.2255949	-2.4707584
C	-1.3069335	2.9658627	-1.2926930
C	-0.8713747	2.4484996	-0.0749794
C	-0.3061729	1.1748434	-0.0517811
C	-0.1781085	0.4346385	-1.2416096
C	-0.6212468	0.9482721	-2.4519118
C	0.4458229	-0.9174601	-0.9554031
C	-0.5551301	-2.0291592	-1.2471329
C	0.7060826	-0.8412137	0.5371139
C	1.2774385	-1.7935390	1.3688158
C	1.3994596	-1.5062931	2.7293306
C	0.9458642	-0.2889713	3.2423434
C	0.3629896	0.6644639	2.4107914
C	0.2417642	0.3835505	1.0511828
H	-1.5292776	2.6473037	-3.4078918
H	-1.7474365	3.9560486	-1.3277444
H	-0.9707263	3.0294844	0.8352022
H	-0.5288537	0.3737160	-3.3673017
H	1.3487021	-1.1078814	-1.5400581
H	-1.5203246	-1.9217829	-0.7117022
H	1.6268392	-2.7406304	0.9720022
H	1.8493434	-2.2344927	3.3945474
H	1.0487204	-0.0847865	4.3022939
H	0.0126007	1.6066355	2.8174868
O	-0.3435498	-2.9593276	-1.9885154

Structure 5

26

Energy = -615.5734462

C	0.1181160	-0.0261023	-3.7229189
C	1.4111163	-0.0662679	-3.2020685
C	1.6061167	-0.0511766	-1.8310223
C	0.5269625	0.0116555	-0.9292892
C	-0.7742790	0.0468826	-1.4666058
C	-0.9591328	0.0268078	-2.8504702
C	-1.9959584	0.1182201	-0.5854217

C	-1.6989592	-0.0180329	0.8602023
C	-0.4105520	-0.0089987	1.4052509
C	-0.1836701	-0.0301408	2.8126847
C	1.0905831	-0.0109009	3.3376752
C	2.1980165	0.0342724	2.4825796
C	2.0023242	0.0521933	1.1035628
C	0.7322000	0.0240741	0.5290008
H	-0.0456776	-0.0408357	-4.7944930
H	2.2669332	-0.1145262	-3.8659996
H	2.6199633	-0.0966530	-1.4550403
H	-1.9711877	0.0533369	-3.2436975
H	-2.5192740	1.0738592	-0.7522684
H	-2.7170141	-0.6567049	-0.8783897
H	-1.0215938	-0.0421366	3.5047916
H	1.2313152	-0.0216121	4.4128223
H	3.2027731	0.0580274	2.8871446
H	2.8763607	0.0930256	0.4659021
O	-2.8370176	-0.0785972	1.6137605
H	-2.6069755	-0.1970613	2.5458530

Structure 6

25

Energy = -615.0071606

C	1.7863803	0.6552449	-3.1251650
C	1.9199903	-0.6879586	-2.7802071
C	1.3507597	-1.1606849	-1.6066525
C	0.6449040	-0.3085147	-0.7431744
C	0.5059140	1.0442528	-1.1038293
C	1.0774258	1.5085744	-2.2883054
C	-0.2338796	1.9982918	-0.2053199
C	-1.2463373	1.3634891	0.7239334
C	-0.9348510	-0.0128008	1.1816020
C	-1.5975502	-0.5057423	2.3105259
C	-1.3077668	-1.7672890	2.8033777
C	-0.3481746	-2.5472030	2.1549342
C	0.2992316	-2.0745704	1.0220801
C	0.0169981	-0.8031300	0.4997130
H	2.2210148	1.0315759	-4.0442472
H	2.4569806	-1.3689491	-3.4307101
H	1.4408518	-2.2141611	-1.3718294
H	0.9593670	2.5537509	-2.5562361
H	-0.7209328	2.7961767	-0.7677488
H	0.4919848	2.4858132	0.4635474
H	-2.3306458	0.1342227	2.7878834
H	-1.8118109	-2.1416912	3.6867878
H	-0.1017350	-3.5318823	2.5367848
H	1.0410635	-2.7032656	0.5456214
O	-2.2160773	1.9861720	1.1257949

Structure 7

27

Energy = -690.8082077

C	1.9396366	1.4646641	-3.1783486
C	2.8249931	0.7031193	-2.4187368
C	2.3872987	0.0917397	-1.2534490
C	1.0616594	0.2272390	-0.8093838
C	0.1737279	0.9953430	-1.5840966
C	0.6234134	1.6020078	-2.7572984
C	-1.2508805	1.1966740	-1.1492341
C	-1.7515865	0.2841873	-0.0550706
C	-0.7786453	-0.4288411	0.7457388
C	-1.3358467	-1.2115672	1.9157561
C	-0.2911225	-1.8180853	2.7844064
C	1.0236784	-1.7948715	2.4393806
C	1.4668371	-1.1465279	1.2643641
C	0.5744281	-0.4488411	0.4139272
H	2.2717870	1.9419230	-4.0933203
H	3.8538439	0.5800918	-2.7369753
H	3.0911493	-0.5097543	-0.6928894
H	-0.0740598	2.1892280	-3.3464795
H	-1.3627245	2.2148381	-0.7508489
H	-1.9404293	1.1325060	-1.9947974
H	-1.9295189	-2.0405590	1.4809114
H	-0.6363991	-2.2792885	3.7020981
H	1.7609874	-2.2654679	3.0808602
H	2.5255293	-1.1584596	1.0444294
H	-2.9102223	-0.1334852	2.1484595
O	-2.9659257	0.2096491	0.1790059
O	-2.2030225	-0.4326291	2.7489968

Structure 8'

27

Energy = -690.7406065

C	0.2383456	-3.8650838	-0.4485365
C	1.2531401	-3.1146529	-1.0519723
C	1.3466006	-1.7453317	-0.7949404
C	0.4552585	-1.1079224	0.0601361
C	-0.5693646	-1.8688592	0.7158308
C	-0.6533277	-3.2573755	0.4128217
C	-1.4394514	-1.2931865	1.6572921
C	-1.6303682	0.8055822	-0.7053247
C	-0.4632208	1.2453306	-0.2574746
C	-0.1781021	2.7415197	-0.4333235
C	0.7974048	3.2004602	0.6059647
C	1.6578595	2.3417950	1.1775637
C	1.6093840	0.9183030	0.9288875
C	0.5680197	0.3568552	0.2676262
H	0.1533341	-4.9264766	-0.6538805
H	1.9577560	-3.5882041	-1.7257583
H	2.1142567	-1.1527307	-1.2801605
H	-1.4293545	-3.8430100	0.8948595
H	-2.2106723	-1.8903918	2.1281667

H	-1.3454401	-0.2569315	1.9551869
H	-1.1144862	3.3052397	-0.3593516
H	0.8338013	4.2639660	0.8086103
H	2.4087541	2.7131130	1.8674944
H	2.3816914	0.2787675	1.3393740
O	-2.6746203	0.4932697	-1.1109089
H	-0.2047550	2.8150936	-2.4038258
O	0.4383649	3.0242258	-1.7100851

Structure 8"

27

Energy = -690.747408

C	3.7689556	-0.6466392	-0.5573682
C	2.7189767	-1.4417925	-1.0322829
C	1.4031190	-1.0304107	-0.8356411
C	1.0947706	0.1623634	-0.1791480
C	2.1617540	0.9689846	0.3514059
C	3.4962890	0.5264833	0.1142779
C	1.9439573	2.1148331	1.1316771
C	-0.9070671	-1.4836018	1.1106908
C	-1.2881313	-0.4001501	0.4459340
C	-2.7864566	-0.2274649	0.1955276
C	-3.1123690	1.2321728	0.0913413
C	-2.1783270	2.1351276	-0.2689786
C	-0.7874881	1.7887768	-0.4304255
C	-0.3223228	0.5627732	-0.0629176
H	4.7969263	-0.9548282	-0.7127385
H	2.9244738	-2.3638328	-1.5632376
H	0.5907496	-1.6294679	-1.2338258
H	4.3104639	1.1310489	0.5003766
H	2.7876781	2.6817214	1.5065071
H	0.9504528	2.4323185	1.4149168
H	-3.3597228	-0.7077600	0.9883475
H	-4.1514899	1.5120040	0.2191538
H	-2.4690689	3.1665820	-0.4414084
H	-0.0991180	2.5215362	-0.8328058
H	-2.8781234	-0.4245778	-1.7522371
O	-0.6377612	-2.4416399	1.7079758
O	-3.2159954	-0.9260809	-0.9954940

Structure 8

27

Energy = -690.7454177

C	0.2601548	3.8563874	-0.4587175
C	1.1953231	2.9975456	-1.0461237
C	1.1877742	1.6432332	-0.7147475
C	0.2698452	1.1160519	0.1910254
C	-0.7092763	1.9804204	0.7877464
C	-0.6647123	3.3608950	0.4371295
C	-1.7097091	1.5134818	1.6556626
C	0.0508557	-0.9303456	-1.8255578

C	0.1936198	-1.3008922	-0.5575713
C	0.0064423	-2.7964175	-0.2698706
C	0.5629037	-3.1333582	1.0801148
C	0.7414038	-2.1958350	2.0305604
C	0.5632860	-0.7870807	1.7738281
C	0.3301206	-0.3289557	0.5154167
H	0.2620139	4.9121301	-0.7060067
H	1.9303812	3.3797992	-1.7446507
H	1.9343122	0.9845658	-1.1470777
H	-1.3950782	4.0264270	0.8856680
H	-1.8027689	0.4654709	1.9037617
H	-2.4269358	2.2054590	2.0804106
H	0.4722752	-3.3952917	-1.0528873
H	0.7221631	-4.1854781	1.2856686
H	1.0576066	-2.4953778	3.0246856
H	0.6890050	-0.0772766	2.5821549
H	-1.8290094	-2.7994864	0.4213870
O	-0.0607374	-0.6799096	-2.9529557
O	-1.3845720	-3.1868096	-0.3470930

Structure 9

27

Energy = -690.8158074

C	0.1693316	3.7162021	-0.5530239
C	1.1494744	2.8821364	-1.1009472
C	1.1992260	1.5370821	-0.7345535
C	0.2923386	1.0040285	0.1721724
C	-0.7282432	1.8392434	0.7365340
C	-0.7483117	3.2079912	0.3433025
C	-1.7020126	1.3507743	1.6247839
C	-0.3542335	-1.2949444	-1.6640279
C	0.0775435	-1.4998857	-0.2409169
C	0.1711731	-2.8137538	0.2367743
C	0.6048840	-3.0706050	1.5308419
C	0.9224800	-2.0058663	2.3695468
C	0.8113901	-0.7002774	1.9061686
C	0.4036648	-0.4182533	0.5966319
H	0.1265415	4.7621994	-0.8359664
H	1.8680199	3.2736541	-1.8113725
H	1.9490716	0.8877118	-1.1678550
H	-1.5151095	3.8517010	0.7619162
H	-1.7354448	0.3113213	1.9223289
H	-2.4568796	2.0163169	2.0258384
H	-0.0685394	-3.6395920	-0.4255735
H	0.6946006	-4.0926192	1.8803387
H	1.2582206	-2.1912214	3.3837258
H	1.0473661	0.1301876	2.5620355
H	-1.9339828	-2.2822736	-1.2021669
O	0.2579248	-0.6790426	-2.4955798
O	-1.5233201	-1.9179240	-2.0011870

Structure 10

26

Energy = -615.5628305

C	2.9448139	0.7167888	-2.4254098
C	3.3229239	-0.1114823	-1.3519207
C	2.4113637	-0.4521225	-0.3762958
C	1.0778771	0.0157329	-0.4175091
C	0.6998694	0.8574907	-1.5079459
C	1.6561539	1.1892716	-2.4979279
C	-0.6300571	1.3494731	-1.5823395
C	-1.5505589	1.0281464	-0.6161305
C	-1.2081127	0.2025615	0.4704962
C	-2.2950727	-0.1156555	1.4774483
C	-1.8501505	-1.0054147	2.5903017
C	-0.5759676	-1.4904051	2.6613272
C	0.3985280	-1.1600753	1.6996996
C	0.0928191	-0.3181401	0.5922820
H	3.6687872	0.9790007	-3.1886101
H	4.3393105	-0.4843917	-1.2913600
H	2.7348551	-1.0906480	0.4358028
H	1.3502008	1.8292100	-3.3192529
H	-0.9059920	1.9875881	-2.4153468
H	-2.5695057	1.3927453	-0.6849889
H	-2.6833683	0.8239757	1.8895995
H	-2.5994465	-1.2700167	3.3277594
H	-0.2976042	-2.1507115	3.4764325
H	1.3916640	-1.5742936	1.8080230
H	-3.1975056	-1.5081854	0.4239649
O	-3.4703483	-0.6676911	0.8205454

Structure 11

25

Energy = -614.8913247

C	-3.6314867	1.2355504	-0.6072836
C	-2.6897743	1.9787159	-1.3436211
C	-1.3457235	1.6908806	-1.2524182
C	-0.8696281	0.6508964	-0.4215132
C	-1.8292292	-0.1004723	0.3233130
C	-3.2045286	0.2155315	0.2084230
C	-1.3909260	-1.1565728	1.1644321
C	-0.0559108	-1.4560004	1.2733967
C	0.9093260	-0.7268284	0.5600498
C	2.3681374	-1.1184380	0.7351061
C	3.3348994	-0.3371158	-0.1031028
C	2.9034768	0.6647640	-0.9228793
C	1.5460025	1.0224675	-1.0184994
C	0.5365347	0.3257955	-0.2935495
H	-4.6872679	1.4687102	-0.6864126
H	-3.0240138	2.7840754	-1.9881624
H	-0.6480786	2.2815953	-1.8323225
H	-3.9192216	-0.3670307	0.7808155

H	-2.1295615	-1.7243673	1.7203959
H	0.2738960	-2.2756211	1.9026281
H	2.6330268	-0.9428140	1.8115460
H	4.3762105	-0.6287258	-0.0423800
H	3.6263740	1.2032139	-1.5275157
H	1.2736789	1.8293580	-1.6850074
O	2.5942167	-2.4843287	0.6499483

Structure 12 (triplet)

25

Energy = -614.8758386

C	-3.7652016	-0.4030235	-0.9901876
C	-2.9092780	-0.2552748	-2.0709912
C	-1.5385820	-0.0567241	-1.8578466
C	-0.9980917	0.0091164	-0.5748042
C	-1.8767591	-0.1727971	0.5361327
C	-3.2466578	-0.3671596	0.3044072
C	-1.3474377	-0.1826147	1.8664781
C	0.0380053	-0.0627298	2.0946427
C	0.9186121	0.1389219	1.0669911
C	2.3702429	0.2338144	1.3221897
C	3.2648700	0.6496272	0.2334953
C	2.6704358	0.9311156	-1.0737100
C	1.3021734	0.6911377	-1.3047059
C	0.4269456	0.2708092	-0.3225338
H	-4.8272928	-0.5542845	-1.1458777
H	-3.2919871	-0.2973863	-3.0842266
H	-0.8904236	0.0368632	-2.7208178
H	-3.9069621	-0.4940674	1.1563045
H	-2.0268876	-0.3226202	2.6994679
H	0.4148804	-0.1320661	3.1103857
H	2.6563659	0.4477371	2.3501089
H	4.2025822	1.1389495	0.4815049
H	3.3108240	1.2507315	-1.8868887
H	0.9303447	0.8596090	-2.3086818
O	3.2133959	-0.7525344	0.6746348

Structure 12 (singlet)

25

Energy = -614.9534744

C	-3.7405316	-0.3968334	-0.9663270
C	-2.8671638	-0.2047705	-2.0566250
C	-1.5221793	-0.0087659	-1.8496775
C	-0.9702793	0.0049957	-0.5436879
C	-1.8601501	-0.2025202	0.5584828
C	-3.2420930	-0.3978282	0.3125070
C	-1.3461429	-0.2080214	1.8784913
C	-0.0042661	-0.0459409	2.1046465
C	0.8927590	0.1393878	1.0323985
C	2.3371951	0.2435582	1.3107964
C	3.2554031	0.6304802	0.1996023

C	2.6468864	0.8873042	-1.1097677
C	1.3479501	0.6129453	-1.3354576
C	0.4282874	0.2096633	-0.2846501
H	-4.7995434	-0.5488823	-1.1420066
H	-3.2593276	-0.2163853	-3.0674461
H	-0.8757788	0.1176916	-2.7086314
H	-3.9020430	-0.5515685	1.1602915
H	-2.0303240	-0.3603434	2.7065782
H	0.3869240	-0.0748069	3.1164610
H	2.6213517	0.4768458	2.3347666
H	4.1896395	1.1310120	0.4396487
H	3.2668039	1.3059847	-1.8945564
H	0.9481965	0.7911004	-2.3257550
O	3.1925430	-0.7291521	0.6853885

Structure 13

25

Energy = -614.9283183

C	3.6399295	0.8967523	0.9972789
C	3.4461131	0.7756683	-0.3825050
C	2.1980298	0.4407851	-0.8830901
C	1.1070188	0.2200023	-0.0278647
C	1.3124695	0.3150286	1.3722223
C	2.5832674	0.6635827	1.8601786
C	0.2187774	0.0395911	2.2741284
C	-0.9672304	-0.4182088	1.8204419
C	-1.1950889	-0.6356606	0.4084218
C	-2.3118804	-1.3097743	0.0092606
C	-2.8561313	-0.6535359	-1.9470489
C	-1.9592664	0.3000336	-2.2891595
C	-0.6345060	0.3718636	-1.7776082
C	-0.2342247	-0.0829747	-0.5360085
H	4.6161005	1.1585659	1.3895094
H	4.2752844	0.9315031	-1.0634454
H	2.0692562	0.3197766	-1.9526415
H	2.7283152	0.7397425	2.9331957
H	0.3889844	0.1619620	3.3387323
H	-1.7561211	-0.6921738	2.5132047
H	-3.1113187	-1.5909454	0.6890969
H	-3.9042855	-0.6439715	-2.2280310
H	-2.2950877	1.0849045	-2.9601618
H	0.0649022	0.9897395	-2.3305032
O	-2.4300693	-1.8081440	-1.2843063

Structure 14'

26

Energy = -690.1236932

C	0.5082211	-4.0477620	0.1573915
C	1.6668313	-3.2647076	0.0311459
C	1.5814824	-1.8931841	-0.0912078
C	0.3315563	-1.2246720	-0.1117078

C	-0.8382777	-2.0307080	0.0501588
C	-0.7241249	-3.4284218	0.1739714
C	-2.1143956	-1.3932638	0.0937906
C	-2.2250867	-0.0449758	0.0065302
C	-1.0807056	0.8146681	-0.1463800
C	-1.4097990	2.1686535	-0.2501770
C	0.7235808	3.2531029	0.1907865
C	1.6552722	2.2780204	-0.4915046
C	1.3943899	0.9537082	-0.5987797
C	0.2128848	0.2065994	-0.2558443
H	0.5847288	-5.1244820	0.2546572
H	2.6420391	-3.7389685	0.0437390
H	2.5014388	-1.3248202	-0.1418892
H	-1.6309230	-4.0132457	0.2897208
H	-3.0006447	-2.0083444	0.2098622
H	-3.2040874	0.4204641	0.0516600
H	-2.4577559	2.4434300	-0.2888358
H	1.0306216	4.2929707	0.0250592
H	2.6236722	2.6722595	-0.7712837
H	2.1914598	0.3730019	-1.0529188
O	-0.6309901	3.2536510	-0.3687174
O	0.8123493	2.8568861	1.4599707

Structure 14 (triplet)

26

Energy = -690.1485871

C	1.0203968	2.2059704	3.2284114
C	2.0687276	1.4484774	2.6933463
C	1.8466621	0.6055724	1.6161152
C	0.5734485	0.4713890	1.0403321
C	-0.4963859	1.2244335	1.6042141
C	-0.2450113	2.0902208	2.6874658
C	-1.8217236	1.0732617	1.0872265
C	-2.0954916	0.1366205	0.1191773
C	-1.0780123	-0.6416220	-0.4527512
C	-1.4956113	-1.8082345	-1.2145465
C	0.4096822	-0.7759575	-3.3004776
C	1.2775358	-1.2982219	-2.2780577
C	1.3466673	-0.8060476	-0.9376866
C	0.3087438	-0.3576676	-0.1451546
H	1.1993737	2.8710747	4.0652175
H	3.0615279	1.5168799	3.1233071
H	2.6781380	0.0261452	1.2343731
H	-1.0701766	2.6637542	3.0966244
H	-2.6212199	1.6599910	1.5263100
H	-3.1214773	-0.0468588	-0.1842984
H	-2.5878146	-1.8792405	-1.3711194
H	0.5348232	-1.2291924	-4.2991198
H	2.0121278	-2.0325102	-2.5936101
H	2.3575198	-0.7075703	-0.5512575
O	-0.4492713	0.0915142	-3.1148134

O -0.7621538 -2.6925624 -1.6524247

Structure 14 (singlet)

26

Energy = -690.2096441

C	1.1531160	2.3905880	2.5422478
C	2.1127771	1.6307336	1.8396585
C	1.7190365	0.6315488	0.9853897
C	0.3458468	0.3398480	0.7839649
C	-0.6248444	1.1006606	1.5110403
C	-0.1846671	2.1277736	2.3808007
C	-2.0041899	0.8166641	1.3493375
C	-2.4069633	-0.1934076	0.5222530
C	-1.4605387	-0.9612754	-0.2008887
C	-1.9662356	-2.0405516	-1.0601438
C	1.6102224	0.2410555	-2.4904782
C	1.6608989	-1.0907704	-1.8700748
C	0.8739879	-1.5054950	-0.8614815
C	-0.0960565	-0.6871584	-0.1038617
H	1.4764696	3.1801294	3.2113071
H	3.1676726	1.8393070	1.9769873
H	2.4611216	0.0548465	0.4482121
H	-0.9280230	2.7040314	2.9216441
H	-2.7296652	1.4100307	1.8953033
H	-3.4617341	-0.4200392	0.4014422
H	-3.0708457	-2.1471290	-1.0610963
H	2.3259831	0.3858902	-3.3258915
H	2.3478706	-1.8005833	-2.3212945
H	0.9481953	-2.5452895	-0.5556707
O	0.8610169	1.1453598	-2.1676796
O	-1.2794272	-2.7971486	-1.7242241

Structure 15

25

Energy = -614.9297678

C	0.1307514	-0.0118319	-3.7852026
C	1.3770820	0.2529900	-3.2094080
C	1.5113677	0.3098958	-1.8323689
C	0.4111287	0.1114056	-0.9801201
C	-0.8554946	-0.1370590	-1.5697337
C	-0.9696719	-0.2017555	-2.9673386
C	-2.0296727	-0.2902661	-0.7342251
C	-1.9807673	-0.1304993	0.5980067
C	-0.7132197	0.1497660	1.2710743
C	-0.5796619	-0.1720980	2.7887318
C	0.7353432	-0.5170077	3.2829098
C	1.8330794	-0.2684224	2.5218890
C	1.7296663	0.0653169	1.1391408
C	0.5306896	0.1272360	0.4769334
H	0.0254984	-0.0600210	-4.8630337

H	2.2437864	0.4152064	-3.8402680
H	2.4851768	0.5274771	-1.4111665
H	-1.9447980	-0.3964852	-3.4024766
H	-2.9749282	-0.4977722	-1.2258932
H	-2.8726484	-0.1728214	1.2127458
H	-1.4523431	-0.5914423	3.2842544
H	0.8164778	-1.0112270	4.2444287
H	2.8219358	-0.4652625	2.9220501
H	2.6534152	0.1013681	0.5739167
O	-0.7877936	1.1546531	2.3040495

Structure 16 (singlet)

25

Energy = -614.9509294

C	2.0146201	3.1807082	-0.5550369
C	2.6460867	2.2175785	0.2579196
C	2.0004624	1.0507189	0.5934437
C	0.6819390	0.7823472	0.1454355
C	0.0544715	1.7538762	-0.6983639
C	0.7463978	2.9461740	-1.0249504
C	-1.2450248	1.5022840	-1.2012531
C	-1.8982172	0.3384164	-0.8907772
C	-1.2906487	-0.6022813	-0.0413293
C	-1.5780925	-2.9120224	-0.0976772
C	-0.4477412	-3.4325813	0.3895935
C	0.4116973	-2.7419570	1.3312969
C	0.5792131	-1.4040897	1.3913226
C	-0.0252437	-0.4201220	0.4976392
H	2.5345830	4.0963480	-0.8130972
H	3.6543562	2.3948534	0.6156139
H	2.5197650	0.3183940	1.1980719
H	0.2525377	3.6723953	-1.6626433
H	-1.7190075	2.2454450	-1.8336346
H	-2.8973391	0.1290131	-1.2526540
H	-2.2228570	-3.4211370	-0.8064397
H	-0.1753931	-4.4333866	0.0704270
H	0.9983883	-3.3607335	2.0039707
H	1.2806215	-1.0223342	2.1254023
O	-2.0839853	-1.6914912	0.3321618

Structure 16 (triplet)

25

Energy = -614.9037245

C	1.9390424	3.3565066	-0.3209194
C	2.6487248	2.3224426	0.2976669
C	2.0752225	1.0714787	0.4518063
C	0.7688415	0.7894050	0.0079760
C	0.0678135	1.8399696	-0.6525043
C	0.6668093	3.1067059	-0.7950602
C	-1.2288437	1.5904941	-1.1972701
C	-1.7883741	0.3440422	-1.1047391

C	-1.1363138	-0.7058581	-0.4456330
C	-1.7065975	-3.0766962	0.0204867
C	-0.6913755	-3.5241130	0.8527207
C	0.4078991	-2.8233041	1.3109370
C	0.7692155	-1.4763568	1.0093164
C	0.1379708	-0.5305883	0.2055669
H	2.3874387	4.3364171	-0.4388655
H	3.6586989	2.4927727	0.6535231
H	2.6728674	0.2965100	0.9129343
H	0.1057977	3.8887822	-1.2965937
H	-1.7549748	2.3928673	-1.7014169
H	-2.7574613	0.1291083	-1.5387245
H	-2.5231794	-3.7184708	-0.2783242
H	-0.8036786	-4.5573522	1.1647167
H	1.0849692	-3.3537723	1.9711102
H	1.6798313	-1.1536821	1.4955072
O	-1.8887546	-1.8508919	-0.5097761

Structure 17

25

Energy = -614.8412493

C	-1.5888188	-3.3658248	-0.7861387
C	-0.1861948	-3.3186712	-0.7185650
C	0.4662765	-2.1220560	-0.4999467
C	-0.2471790	-0.9149459	-0.3469004
C	-1.6752336	-0.9674848	-0.4000377
C	-2.3155643	-2.2083373	-0.6243769
C	-2.4449671	0.2157940	-0.2084832
C	-1.8352554	1.4297501	0.0401067
C	-0.4527619	1.4532518	0.0644919
C	1.3641349	3.2609428	1.6790726
C	2.4378783	2.8121920	0.8286008
C	2.6210862	1.6330238	0.1202316
C	1.8061536	0.5325127	-0.1899451
C	0.3989045	0.3758078	-0.1201081
H	-2.0930183	-4.3102282	-0.9562729
H	0.3900562	-4.2303217	-0.8315170
H	1.5469024	-2.1228221	-0.4288025
H	-3.3999189	-2.2318978	-0.6623866
H	-3.5275944	0.1429931	-0.2523495
H	-2.4165782	2.3290361	0.2092346
H	1.5684656	4.2261882	2.1805650
H	3.2954373	3.4802176	0.8405975
H	3.6348360	1.5201688	-0.2594833
H	2.3532989	-0.3066224	-0.6068515
O	0.3036782	2.6835404	1.9315682

TS 2→3

26

Energy = -615.511989

C	-3.4156218	-1.0282348	0.6157930
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C	-2.8493284	-0.8365424	1.8785788
C	-1.5230148	-0.4355324	2.0044286
C	-0.7502373	-0.2400211	0.8577986
C	-1.3131792	-0.4832183	-0.4190662
C	-2.6496676	-0.8530535	-0.5366053
C	-0.3408157	-0.3424907	-1.5087750
C	0.9036066	-1.1147165	-1.3417726
C	1.1375306	0.1984677	-0.5920580
C	2.1720502	1.0939566	-1.0049606
C	2.6858265	2.0064395	-0.1101869
C	2.2117168	2.0696937	1.2139305
C	1.1503567	1.2565698	1.6183816
C	0.5737870	0.3558942	0.7365463
H	-4.4547069	-1.3254828	0.5299161
H	-3.4516511	-0.9895505	2.7669790
H	-1.0971047	-0.2625922	2.9869906
H	-3.0873998	-1.0198273	-1.5149999
H	-0.5798670	0.1089078	-2.4665309
H	0.8625896	-2.0007813	-0.7117371
H	2.6098720	0.9850091	-1.9899282
H	3.4898671	2.6644206	-0.4216195
H	2.6416358	2.7820453	1.9081876
H	0.7227878	1.3820029	2.6078071
O	1.7188778	-1.3739111	-2.4524413
H	1.4670550	-0.7830571	-3.1740855

TS 2→5

26

Energy = -615.4994142

C	0.1135783	0.7814060	3.6642298
C	1.1359193	1.4556025	2.9949349
C	1.2785168	1.3018800	1.6183463
C	0.4197981	0.4915606	0.8701800
C	-0.6282344	-0.1860871	1.5599903
C	-0.7582228	-0.0254188	2.9536048
C	-1.5656305	-0.9904696	0.8333118
C	-1.4027698	-1.1796562	-0.6252644
C	-0.2703217	-0.5938689	-1.3031394
C	-0.0197329	-0.8661989	-2.6598477
C	1.0246726	-0.2485392	-3.3340884
C	1.8478092	0.6460074	-2.6581325
C	1.6339531	0.8931712	-1.3017990
C	0.5968263	0.2873616	-0.5895288
H	-0.0027680	0.8902240	4.7369258
H	1.8207154	2.0947262	3.5397071
H	2.0863874	1.8286164	1.1263264
H	-1.5582539	-0.5491359	3.4664418
H	-2.3075656	-1.6033925	1.3260891
H	-2.1810235	-0.2702788	-0.0845609
H	-0.6396258	-1.5810223	-3.1907302
H	1.1966517	-0.4701087	-4.3814669

H	2.6631894	1.1399234	-3.1733061
H	2.3116037	1.5661925	-0.7923280
O	-2.1065454	-2.2504997	-1.1451782
H	-2.3247219	-2.0624015	-2.0682118

TS 7→8'

27

Energy = -690.7339384

C	-1.4337521	-3.4562895	-0.0443068
C	-0.0919516	-3.4009600	0.3543517
C	0.5280729	-2.1739160	0.5780873
C	-0.1834646	-0.9814684	0.4519505
C	-1.5713431	-1.0397218	0.1335993
C	-2.1614134	-2.2881872	-0.1732818
C	-2.3314892	0.1594083	0.1534056
C	-1.0914650	1.4204114	-1.1275486
C	0.0991925	1.3355847	-0.4999840
C	1.1251968	2.3900181	-0.9049641
C	1.9637561	2.7668770	0.2785295
C	2.1729745	1.8921227	1.2803008
C	1.5234445	0.6066706	1.3150779
C	0.4851529	0.3268814	0.4779870
H	-1.8998890	-4.4130595	-0.2494217
H	0.4814291	-4.3162756	0.4480088
H	1.5895280	-2.1362922	0.7935147
H	-3.2081013	-2.3193488	-0.4560322
H	-3.3291124	0.1686056	-0.2706211
H	-2.1171918	0.9178824	0.8965492
H	0.6021335	3.2676310	-1.2993875
H	2.4501137	3.7350826	0.2582716
H	2.8432895	2.1515262	2.0934338
H	1.8332183	-0.1235650	2.0533689
O	-1.8400989	1.8831690	-1.9225612
H	1.5254271	1.7304667	-2.7150354
O	2.0423685	1.8998460	-1.9133202

TS 8"→8

27

Energy = -690.7331

C	-1.7722161	-3.3044560	-0.1026372
C	-0.5301010	-3.1233694	0.5194787
C	0.0317065	-1.8559557	0.5717035
C	-0.5765386	-0.7097534	0.0283125
C	-1.9574373	-0.8631832	-0.4108332
C	-2.4589047	-2.2000694	-0.5446519
C	-2.8932906	0.1482668	-0.6333393
C	2.4667899	-0.5922757	-0.1111628
C	1.6895078	0.4460085	0.1410574
C	2.4571916	1.7024551	0.5612111
C	1.9333169	2.8766323	-0.2048797
C	0.6655885	2.8705543	-0.6639550

C	-0.2077859	1.7370892	-0.5216861
C	0.2357772	0.5074069	-0.1039178
H	-2.2054209	-4.2935991	-0.1967130
H	0.0010854	-3.9636385	0.9507451
H	0.9843713	-1.7510536	1.0737100
H	-3.4554325	-2.3150294	-0.9582229
H	-3.8798039	-0.1253154	-0.9897988
H	-2.7562882	1.1787816	-0.3522419
H	3.5219658	1.5596428	0.3762189
H	2.5756932	3.7437304	-0.3038714
H	0.2629434	3.7543622	-1.1483970
H	-1.2327677	1.8782938	-0.8158796
H	1.4772369	2.1960483	2.1815684
O	3.2380559	-1.4398947	-0.3195799
O	2.3883890	1.9360821	1.9810851

TS 8→9

27

Energy = -690.7096086

C	-1.8951292	3.3947055	-0.8584892
C	-1.0732043	2.7887901	-1.8171582
C	-0.2626014	1.7202431	-1.4485638
C	-0.2349443	1.2320330	-0.1403725
C	-1.1194728	1.8048247	0.8408066
C	-1.9153081	2.9161403	0.4339245
C	-1.2851962	1.2847642	2.1323594
C	-0.2326429	-1.5269425	-1.3612197
C	0.8482987	-0.9642213	-0.7026960
C	1.8372784	-2.0333103	-0.5229448
C	2.4997690	-2.0383300	0.7493649
C	2.3283630	-0.9730178	1.6018327
C	1.5037446	0.1438312	1.3150405
C	0.7161481	0.1558611	0.1778274
H	-2.5213476	4.2362303	-1.1334437
H	-1.0562316	3.1552812	-2.8367748
H	0.3981615	1.2687172	-2.1803271
H	-2.5734980	3.3682276	1.1686570
H	-0.7866723	0.3823327	2.4563601
H	-1.9689837	1.7638666	2.8228629
H	2.4064302	-2.3790609	-1.3813245
H	3.1993006	-2.8303925	0.9887381
H	2.8981415	-0.9571460	2.5261624
H	1.4912991	0.9902256	1.9890548
H	0.1487817	-3.4400714	-0.0996342
O	-1.2564421	-1.5368632	-1.9191760
O	0.5594150	-3.2284454	-0.9549284

TS 10→11

28

Energy = -691.3319684

C	-3.7148036	1.6213310	-0.4043354
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C	-2.8627001	1.9836858	-1.4642819
C	-1.5369780	1.6083219	-1.4561388
C	-0.9914801	0.8567196	-0.3905715
C	-1.8602725	0.4909728	0.6824871
C	-3.2185744	0.8881859	0.6469159
C	-1.3497219	-0.2659940	1.7699952
C	-0.0316011	-0.6464172	1.8012068
C	0.8483867	-0.2957654	0.7619357
C	2.2759167	-0.8033328	0.8454591
C	3.1527898	-0.3613710	-0.2782866
C	2.6660063	0.3652238	-1.3251875
C	1.3200084	0.7738955	-1.3822145
C	0.3987109	0.4458511	-0.3463727
H	-4.7565333	1.9208020	-0.4202855
H	-3.2514767	2.5633291	-2.2939762
H	-0.9086494	1.9038488	-2.2865907
H	-3.8638354	0.6013747	1.4708105
H	-2.0203312	-0.5398387	2.5774488
H	0.3488978	-1.2426540	2.6228135
H	2.7019747	-0.4833933	1.8098399
H	4.1860488	-0.6867967	-0.2467527
H	3.3262738	0.6364095	-2.1422411
H	0.9891731	1.3433639	-2.2397545
H	2.0212929	-2.7037337	0.0384295
O	2.2874021	-2.2380292	0.9899887
O	1.1814653	-3.0280435	-0.8745668
H	0.5819112	-2.2668446	-0.9815086

TS 11→12 (triplet)

25

Energy = -614.8695606

C	-1.5378126	-3.3861109	0.0002526
C	-0.1442053	-3.3895414	-0.0769388
C	0.5574703	-2.1892330	-0.0956099
C	-0.0981909	-0.9537630	-0.0365185
C	-1.5210045	-0.9530900	0.0475110
C	-2.2138998	-2.1790829	0.0629173
C	-2.2299800	0.2851230	0.1212647
C	-1.5451220	1.4988603	0.1302006
C	-0.1687668	1.5530151	0.0373060
C	0.5365501	2.8649730	0.1625437
C	1.9732700	2.8987970	-0.1562137
C	2.6640084	1.6930373	-0.3056298
C	1.9825263	0.4262279	-0.2173620
C	0.6190426	0.3292823	-0.0691794
H	-2.0872080	-4.3205328	0.0137825
H	0.3970464	-4.3277098	-0.1222198
H	1.6384872	-2.2248741	-0.1511910
H	-3.2971131	-2.1633773	0.1262011
H	-3.3127958	0.2654695	0.1742105
H	-2.1032865	2.4265535	0.2100383

H	-0.0677411	3.7147282	-0.1693383
H	2.4443532	3.8510023	-0.3525643
H	3.7354816	1.7039355	-0.4672502
H	2.5879625	-0.4665675	-0.3030612
O	1.1969866	3.0669364	1.3931876

TS 12 (singlet)→13

25

Energy = -614.9283126

C	-1.9395897	3.2999262	-0.3899075
C	-1.4996472	2.7362445	-1.5932800
C	-0.8003682	1.5412253	-1.5873735
C	-0.5187012	0.8688111	-0.3863934
C	-0.9411275	1.4560223	0.8345074
C	-1.6574690	2.6660481	0.8061746
C	-0.6218510	0.8100343	2.0826611
C	0.1657235	-0.2875598	2.1230247
C	0.7061206	-0.8630920	0.9145919
C	1.6627296	-1.8421565	1.0055416
C	1.5684309	-3.0738071	-0.6507655
C	0.5494181	-2.6255981	-1.4333407
C	0.0911801	-1.2889392	-1.4372378
C	0.1769686	-0.4181402	-0.3589386
H	-2.4871602	4.2356496	-0.3951721
H	-1.6955207	3.2409416	-2.5326420
H	-0.4383806	1.1324213	-2.5237273
H	-1.9810276	3.1034565	1.7454284
H	-0.9903527	1.2553773	3.0008635
H	0.4592356	-0.7226879	3.0727422
H	1.9500059	-2.3083572	1.9438837
H	1.8314712	-4.1183705	-0.5186106
H	0.0213468	-3.3570175	-2.0376365
H	-0.5457879	-0.9929139	-2.2633402
O	2.4625434	-2.1577239	-0.0889370

TS 14'→14 (triplet)

26

Energy = -690.1144997

C	-1.6185049	-3.4228452	-0.2290731
C	-0.2612585	-3.3788894	0.1019767
C	0.4118054	-2.1678281	0.1832947
C	-0.2254406	-0.9437907	-0.1022037
C	-1.6216313	-0.9980797	-0.3932669
C	-2.2888161	-2.2352640	-0.4603874
C	-2.3337976	0.2223443	-0.5838912
C	-1.6982567	1.4284844	-0.4864028
C	-0.3103517	1.5550237	-0.2105062
C	0.1491288	2.8971883	-0.2878445
C	2.3902928	2.5449939	1.0695716
C	2.7853320	1.2920426	0.4047343
C	1.8807720	0.3096648	0.0396978

C	0.4732570	0.3381523	-0.0566571
H	-2.1408610	-4.3706512	-0.2837300
H	0.2726135	-4.2973357	0.3192937
H	1.4457228	-2.1802193	0.5029255
H	-3.3494042	-2.2397646	-0.6900912
H	-3.3964838	0.1809771	-0.7976069
H	-2.2660776	2.3403751	-0.6413508
H	-0.6235502	3.6355977	-0.5274415
H	3.0823409	3.3936927	1.0610242
H	3.8472637	1.0712278	0.3737973
H	2.3406578	-0.6285028	-0.2554010
O	1.3265185	3.3716755	-0.1636721
O	1.7327926	2.2888358	2.1216943

TS 12 (singlet)→15

25

Energy = -614.8916565

C	-0.8948296	-1.8609523	-3.1768901
C	0.4762168	-1.8779090	-2.8907253
C	0.9634790	-1.2951141	-1.7334783
C	0.1024784	-0.6778025	-0.8092633
C	-1.2872168	-0.6534591	-1.1099387
C	-1.7626450	-1.2510177	-2.2932145
C	-2.1874518	-0.0006659	-0.2081099
C	-1.7523170	0.6243877	0.9225754
C	-0.3830976	0.6031382	1.2745764
C	0.0423228	1.3917920	2.4644289
C	1.4791461	1.2402590	2.8031023
C	2.3491804	0.5526012	2.0091353
C	1.8822970	-0.1208369	0.8600233
C	0.5570368	-0.0684540	0.4365060
H	-1.2681217	-2.3180338	-4.0858108
H	1.1659561	-2.3494961	-3.5817162
H	2.0311953	-1.3172277	-1.5529461
H	-2.8270417	-1.2196057	-2.5024196
H	-3.2459950	-0.0101230	-0.4493762
H	-2.4454564	1.1410074	1.5757522
H	-0.6392917	1.3177843	3.3253716
H	1.8378890	1.8115588	3.6527474
H	3.4108573	0.5469170	2.2265318
H	2.6118488	-0.6502909	0.2578505
O	0.0174687	2.6215672	1.7840637

TS 15→16 (singlet)

25

Energy = -614.9285871

C	1.7778956	3.3537712	-0.3483641
C	2.4020496	2.5149972	0.5845446
C	1.8795212	1.2660265	0.8608138
C	0.7062566	0.8043274	0.2314325
C	0.0695484	1.6646187	-0.7051875

C	0.6275307	2.9269505	-0.9810821
C	-1.1530456	1.2551531	-1.3479532
C	-1.7523342	0.0847949	-1.0472172
C	-1.1397561	-0.8255365	-0.1059014
C	-1.4356915	-2.4916132	-0.3027356
C	-0.3791894	-3.3361187	0.0995369
C	0.5843070	-2.8822838	0.9749125
C	0.8222638	-1.5119292	1.1797112
C	0.1438166	-0.5154507	0.4871518
H	2.1930108	4.3308398	-0.5675691
H	3.3028492	2.8434437	1.0908743
H	2.3848933	0.6392681	1.5849945
H	0.1295750	3.5686643	-1.7010133
H	-1.6116764	1.9384187	-2.0556061
H	-2.7114634	-0.1942013	-1.4672477
H	-2.0904666	-2.7568186	-1.1282809
H	-0.2946353	-4.3147575	-0.3601086
H	1.3091598	-3.5833770	1.3748649
H	1.7153757	-1.2521221	1.7347634
O	-2.0242132	-1.6358872	0.6477068

The DFT/TPSS-D3/SVP optimized structures of the TS 7→8' in Figure 4

QM preoptimized structure

Active atoms : 8 and 7

27

Energy = -690.1399725944

C	1.9596151	1.6709213	-3.1022366
C	2.8313001	0.9588396	-2.2679502
C	2.3151587	0.2118635	-1.2051863
C	0.9259510	0.1403778	-0.9459377
C	0.0454589	0.8707040	-1.7951638
C	0.5825190	1.6243671	-2.8564497
C	-1.4308642	0.8467781	-1.5826139
C	-1.8117036	0.4757895	0.2586892
C	-0.8097712	-0.3832519	0.8450655
C	-1.2364278	-1.0390099	2.1570736
C	-0.2066013	-1.9502928	2.7412647
C	0.9556848	-2.2377172	2.0732901
C	1.2803895	-1.6047607	0.8421584
C	0.4362039	-0.6244894	0.2382921
H	2.3497908	2.2682520	-3.9331544
H	3.9131974	0.9963143	-2.4316119
H	3.0175110	-0.2977352	-0.5397357
H	-0.1038338	2.1859930	-3.5002564
H	-1.9499979	1.7828837	-1.8336369
H	-1.9291053	-0.0110534	-2.0690878
H	-2.1231147	-1.6791993	1.9098543
H	-0.4362856	-2.3842980	3.7202303

H	1.6713908	-2.9490522	2.4996583
H	2.2198460	-1.8774303	0.3545007
H	-2.3626642	0.4133497	2.7314883
O	-2.8597534	0.8344282	0.7707372
O	-1.6200656	-0.0787603	3.1431919

Structure obtained by geometry optimization from the start structure
from woelfling

ZPE = 0.2049310

<S*S> = 0.76571591

27

Energy = -690.1020872

C	-1.4365294	-3.4863763	-0.0369560
C	-0.0850650	-3.4181353	0.3639410
C	0.5282589	-2.1763784	0.5819169
C	-0.1934084	-0.9769240	0.4450300
C	-1.5964342	-1.0490510	0.1312032
C	-2.1783008	-2.3168187	-0.1690352
C	-2.3793642	0.1399253	0.1553053
C	-1.0967961	1.4669972	-1.1491314
C	0.0910118	1.3693350	-0.4968444
C	1.1477899	2.4085464	-0.9142812
C	1.9785714	2.7877411	0.2837610
C	2.1981947	1.8909869	1.2820444
C	1.5411999	0.6048494	1.3053257
C	0.4804793	0.3354946	0.4662026
H	-1.9008129	-4.4572507	-0.2383685
H	0.5020840	-4.3370457	0.4637452
H	1.5999513	-2.1312694	0.7996616
H	-3.2361981	-2.3586122	-0.4502808
H	-3.3918993	0.1381750	-0.2630838
H	-2.1467312	0.9350854	0.8703631
H	0.6295230	3.2997690	-1.3198631
H	2.4697992	3.7666194	0.2750274
H	2.8796655	2.1425219	2.1030268
H	1.8526600	-0.1417319	2.0423881
O	-1.8615798	1.9364052	-1.9319219
H	1.5486568	1.7452939	-2.7144104
O	2.0612997	1.8849478	-1.8947938

The energy profiles of the woelfling calculations for the
practically barrierless reactions using DFT/TPSS-D3/SVP

Figure 1: The energy profile of the woelfling calculation of the OH addition reaction to the duo site of phenanthrene (reaction 1→2), calculated with one unpaired electron in the system.

Figure 2: The energy profile of the woelfling calculation for the attack of OH to the hydrogen of the OH group on structure 3 to form a water and structure 4 (reaction 3→4), calculated using unrestricted DFT and singlet spin multiplicity.

Figure 3: The energy profile of the woelfling calculation for the reaction 5→6 using unrestricted DFT and singlet spin multiplicity

Figure 4: Energy profile of the woelfling calculation for the reaction 6→7 with doublet spin multiplicity

Figure 5: Energy profile of the woelfling calculation for the reaction 13→14 using unrestricted DFT and singlet spin multiplicity

Figure 6 Energy profile of the woelfling calculation for the oxygen atom addition to the molecule 13 (reaction 13→14') using triplet spin multiplicity